

The Influence of Girl-Child Education on Rural Community Development of Yola North Local Government Area, of Adamawa State

*OLIVER Kadmiel. UMAR Auwal, MUSTAPHER Abubakar

*Corresponding author: oliverkadmiel7@gmail.com

Federal College of Education, Yola P. M. B. 2042 Adamawa State, Nigeria

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11525138>

Abstract

This paper investigated the influence of girl-child education on rural community development in the Yola North Local Government Area of Adamawa State. The study explored the relationship between access to education for girls and the socio-economic development of rural communities, with a focus on Yola North Local Government Area. It employed a mixed-methods research approach, combining quantitative and qualitative methods to provide a holistic understanding of this relationship. A stratified sampling method was used to ensure representation across various demographic groups within the area, and the sample size was determined using the Yemane's sample formula. Questionnaires were administered to households, educators, and community leaders to collect respondents' opinions and perceptions related to girl-child education and rural community development. Five (5) Likert scale questions were utilized to gather the information. The research findings were analysed using correlation analysis and descriptive statistical tools. The results suggested a weak positive relationship between the percentage of girls enrolled in schools and community perceptions of development in the area. However, further targeted interventions, such as outreach programs, scholarships, and infrastructure improvements, are recommended to address disparities in enrolment rates and promote equitable access to education.

Key Words: Girl-child Education, Rural Community Development and Yola North Local Government Area.

Introduction:

Girl-child education is widely recognized as a fundamental pillar of sustainable development, playing a pivotal role in the socio-economic advancement of nations worldwide (UNESCO, 2020). Over the years, there has been a growing acknowledgment of the significance of ensuring equal access to education for girls, not only for their individual empowerment but also for the broader development of communities and entire regions (World Bank, 2018). Within the rural community of Yola North Local Government Area, situated in Adamawa State, Nigeria, the issue of girl-child education holds particular relevance.

Despite concerted global efforts to promote girl-child education, rural areas in many developing countries, including Nigeria, continue to grapple with significant challenges in ensuring equitable access to quality education for girls (UNICEF, 2019). Yola North Local Government Area exemplifies this struggle, contending with a myriad of socio-cultural, economic, and infrastructural barriers that impede the educational advancement of its girl children (Federal Ministry of Education Nigeria, 2017). These impediments have profound implications for the overall development trajectory of the rural community.

This research aims to explore the multifaceted dimensions of girl-child education in Yola North Local Government Area and its impact on rural community development. Therefore, the primary objective of this study is to investigate the influence of girl-child education on rural community development in Yola North Local Government Area of Adamawa State, Nigeria. By delving into this intersection between education and development, this research seeks to provide insights that can inform targeted interventions and policies aimed at fostering holistic development in rural communities.

Hypotheses

1. Null Hypothesis (H_{01}): There is no relationship between Girls Enrolled (%) and Community Perceptions (1-5)
2. Alternative Hypothesis (H_{02}): There is a significant relationship between Girls Enrolled (%) and Community Perceptions (1-5).

Methodology

The methodology employed in this study encompassed a mixed-methods research approach, which amalgamated both quantitative and qualitative research methodologies. This comprehensive approach facilitated a holistic comprehension of the intricate relationship between girl-child education and rural community development as suggested by Creswell & Plano Clark, (2018). To ensure adequate representation across diverse demographic groups within the Yola North Local Government Area, a stratified sampling method was utilised (Dillman, Smyth, & Christian, 2014). The determination of the sample size was based on the Yemane's sample formula, taking into account the population size and the desired level of confidence (Yemane, 1967). Quantitative data

on education access and development indicators were gathered through the administration of questionnaires to households, educators, and community leaders (Bryman and Bell, 2015). Additionally, existing statistical data from post-primary educational institutions were collected and analysed to provide quantitative insights into girl-child enrolment (Patton, 2014). The inclusion of five Likert scale questions facilitated the collection of quantitative data on respondents' opinions and perceptions regarding girl-child education and rural community development in the Yola North Local Government Area (Likert, 1932).

The analysis of the research results pertaining to the influence of girl-child education on rural community development in the Yola North Local Government Area of Adamawa State entailed a combination of quantitative and qualitative methods, thereby ensuring a comprehensive understanding of the findings (Creswell, 2014). Correlation analysis was conducted to assess the strength and nature of the relationship between the level of girl-child education and various development indicators, thereby elucidating the impact of education access on development indicators (Field, 2018). Descriptive statistical tools, including the presentation of tables and percentages, were utilised to succinctly summarise and elucidate the quantitative data collected. The analysis of the data entailed the application of the Pearson correlation moment, to calculate r which enabled an in-depth examination of the relationships between variables (Pearson, 1901). Test Statistic (t) formula was used to get the value of t. The result obtained from the t distribution critical value was compared with the calculated value of t to either reject null hypothesis or to accept it. The Qualitative data were coded using NVivo software for easy use of the data in formula for analysis quantitatively.

Presentation of Results

The Correlation between the Level of Girl-Child Education (Measured as the Percentage of Girls Enrolled in Schools), and community development in Yola North Local Government Area result is presented below.

Table 1: Primary Data (Survey Responses of 2023 Enrolment)

S/N	School	Girls Enrolled (%)	Boys Enrolled (%)	Total	Community Perception (1-5)
1	GDSS (JS) Bachure	96 (30%)	227 (70%)	323	4
2	GDSS JS Damilu	316 (39%)	494 (61%)	810	3
3	GJSS Dougire	68(48%)	73 (52%)	141	4
4	GDSS SS Limawa	101 (54%)	86 (46%)	187	5
5	GJSS Limawa	119 (53%)	107 (47%)	226	3
6	GDSS (JS) Gwadabawa	195 (60%)	131 (40%)	326	4
7	GDSS JS Nyibango LAF	111 (45%)	134 (55%)	245	5
8	GDSS SS Rumnde JMT	206 (66%)	139 (40%)	345	4
9	GJSS Bekaji	119 (40%)	181 (60%)	300	4
10	GDSS (JS) Luggere	153 (45%)	184 (55%)	339	3
11	GDSS SS Bekaji	207 (51%)	198 (49%)	405	4
12	GDSS SS Yelwa JMT	277 (55%)	225 (45%)	502	3

The Influence of Girl-Child Education on Rural Community Development of Yola North Local Government Area, of Adamawa State. Pg. 64 - 74

13	GDSS SS Bachure	205 (47%)	235 (53%)	440	4
14	GDSS (JS) Rumde	236 (49%)	242 (51%)	478	5
15	GJSS Nassarawo	246 (49%)	256 (51%)	502	3
16	GDSS SS Old GRA	280 (52%)	256 (48%)	536	4
17	GDSS SS Damilu	244 (47%)	279 (53%)	523	5
18	GDSS (JS) Karewa	191 (40%)	284 (60%)	475	4
19	GDSS (JS) Demsawo	433 (60%)	290 (40%)	723	4
20	GDSS SS Karewa	265 (47%)	298 (53%)	563	3
21	GDSS SS Doubeli	397 (57%)	298 (43%)	695	4
22	GDSS SS Jambutu	366 (54%)	340 (46%)	730	3
23	GDSS (JS) Jambutu	366 (52%)	340 (48%)	706	4
24	GJSS Old GRA	510 (60%)	370 (40%)	880	5
25	GDSS JS Yelwa Jmt	435 (54%)	375 (46%)	810	3
26	GDSS (JS) Doubeli	369 (49%)	376 (51%)	745	4
27	GDSS SS Demsawo	665 (53%)	579 (47%)	1244	5
28	GDSS (JS) Army Barracks	675 (49%)	680 (51%)	1355	4
29	GDSS (JS) Capital	839 (55%)	681(45%)	1520	4
30	GDSS SS Army Barracks	3217 (82%)	684 (18%)	3901	3
31	GDSS SS Capital	502 (40%)	744 (60%)	1248	5
32	TOTAL	12409 (56%)	9814 (45%)	22223	

Source: Adamawa State post Primary Board, Yola, (2024) and Field survey (2024).

Table 2: Worked Correlation Table on Girl's 2023 Enrolment (%) and Community Perception

S/N	School	Girls (X) Enrolled (%)	Community (Y) Perceptions (1-5)	Total	(X ²)	(Y ²)	XY
1	GDSS (JS) Bachure	30%	4	323	900	16	120
2	GDSS JS Damilu	39%	3	810	1521	9	117
3	GJSS Dougire	48%	4	141	2304	16	192
4	GDSS SS Limawa	54%	5	187	2916	25	270
5	GJSS Limawa	53%	3	226	2809	9	159
6	GDSS (JS) Gwadabawa	60%	4	326	3600	16	240
7	GDSS JS Nyibango LAF	45%	5	245	2025	25	225
8	GDSS SS Rumnde JMT	66%	4	345	4356	16	264
9	GJSS Bekaji	40%	4	300	1600	16	160
10	GDSS (JS) Luggere	45%	3	339	2025	9	135
11	GDSS SS Bekaji	51%	4	405	2601	16	204
12	GDSS SS Yelwa JMT	55%	3	502	3025	9	165
13	GDSS SS Bachure	47%	4	440	2209	16	188
14	GDSS (JS) Rumde	49%	5	478	2401	25	245
15	GJSS Nassarawo	49%	3	502	2401	9	147
16	GDSS SS Old GRA	52%	4	536	2704	16	208
17	GDSS SS Damilu	47%	5	523	2209	25	235
18	GDSS (JS) Karewa	40%	4	475	1600	16	160
19	GDSS (JS) Demsawo	60%	4	723	3600	16	240

The Influence of Girl-Child Education on Rural Community Development of Yola North Local Government Area, of Adamawa State. Pg. 64 - 74

20	GDSS SS Karewa	47%	3	563	2209	9	141
21	GDSS SS Doubeli	57%	4	695	3249	16	228
22	GDSS SS Jambutu	54%	3	730	2916	9	162
23	GDSS (JS) Jambutu	52%	4	706	2704	16	208
24	GJSS Old GRA	60%	5	880	3600	25	300
25	GDSS JS Yelwa Jmt	54%	3	810	2916	9	162
26	GDSS (JS) Doubeli	49%	4	745	2401	16	196
27	GDSS SS Demsawo	53%	5	1244	2809	25	265
28	GDSS (JS) Army Barracks	49%	4	1355	2401	16	196
29	GDSS (JS) Capital	55%	4	1520	3025	16	220
30	GDSS SS Army Barracks	82%	3	3901	6724	9	246
31	GDSS SS Capital	40%	5	1248	1600	25	200
32	TOTAL	1582	122	22223	83360	496	6198
	MEAN	51.0	3.9				

Source: Researcher's calculation, (2024).

The results from Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between the percentages of girls enrolled in schools and community perceptions of development is presented on table 3.

Table 3: results of Pearson correlation coefficient (r) between the percentages of girls enrolled in schools and community perceptions of development

Variable 1	Variable 2	Correlation Coefficient (r)	Test Statistic (t)	Degree of Freedom (df)	Percentage error	critical value
Girl's 2023 Enrolment	Community Perception	0.12	0.65	29	0.05	2.05

From the t distribution Critical Value of t, two-tailed test with 29 degrees of freedom (df) and a significance level (α) of 0.05, the critical value from the t-distribution table is approximately 2.05. Since the calculated t-statistic (0.65) falls short of the critical value (approximately 2.05) for a two-tailed test with 29 degrees of freedom at a 5% significance level, we accept the null hypothesis which says that there is no relationship between the percentages (%) of girls Enrolled in secondary schools in Yola North Local Government Area and the Community Perceptions on rural community development.

The Pearson correlation coefficient (r) is 0.12. This suggests a weak positive relationship between the percentage of girls enrolled in schools and community perceptions of development in Yola North Local Government Area. In other words, as the percentage of girls enrolled increases, community perceptions of development tend to become more positive.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1 presented enrolment data for various schools categorized by gender, along with the total enrolment and community perceptions. The table listed several schools along with their locations, presumably in Yola North Local Government Area. The table provided enrolment numbers for both girls and boys in each school, along with the percentage of girls and boys enrolled. For example, in GDSS (JS) Bachure, there was 96 girls enrolled, which constitutes 30% of the total enrolment, while 227 boys were enrolled, constituting 70% of the total enrolment.

The results presented in Table 1, illustrating enrolment data categorized by gender, resonate with the broader research on gender disparities in education (UNESCO, 2020). These findings underscore the significance of examining enrolment percentages for girls and boys in each school, shedding light on potential inequities in access to education based on gender. Moreover, understanding community attitudes towards education is crucial in interpreting these enrolment patterns (Sababa, 2018). Positive perceptions of girls' education may contribute to higher enrolment rates for girls in certain schools, whereas negative attitudes or cultural barriers could impede girls' access to education in other communities. Analysing enrolment trends within Yola North Local Government Area provide valuable insights into the long-term dynamics of girls' and boys' enrolment (Garcia, 2020), helping identify shifts, disparities, and areas for targeted intervention. Gender equity initiatives, as highlighted in the literature (UNESCO, 2020), play a pivotal role in addressing disparities and promoting equal opportunities for all children.

The total number of students enrolled in each school was also provided. The sum of girls and boys enrolled in GDSS (JS) Bachure was 323. Each school was assigned a community perception score ranging from 1 to 5. This score reflected the community's perception or opinion of the school, but the specific criteria or factors influencing these perceptions were not provided in the table. The table also provided overall totals for girls enrolled, boys enrolled, and the total enrolment across all schools listed.

There were variations in the enrolment percentages between girls and boys across different schools. Some schools had a higher percentage of girls enrolled, while others had a higher percentage of boys enrolled. For instance, GDSS (JS) Bachure had a lower percentage of girls enrolled compared to boys, whereas GDSS (JS) Demsawo had a higher percentage of girls enrolled. The total enrolment varied significantly across schools, ranging from as low as 141 to as high as 3901 students. This indicated differences in the sizes of the schools or possibly differences in popularity and accessibility.

The community perception scores ranged from 1 to 5, with higher scores indicating more favourable perceptions. Schools like GDSS SS Limawa, GDSS SS Nybango ALF, GDSS SS Damilu, GDSS SS Old GRA, GDSS SS Demsawo, GDSS SS Capital and GDSS (JS) Rumde had the highest perception scores of 5, while others had scores ranging from 3 to 4. It's important to note that the table did not provide information on what factors

contribute to the community perceptions of each school. But the perceptions were influenced by various factors such as academic performance, infrastructure, teaching quality, extracurricular activities, and community engagement, among others.

Several research studies support the idea that community perceptions of schools are influenced by a variety of factors, including academic performance, infrastructure, teaching quality, extracurricular activities, and community engagement. For example, Mark and Musa (2018) found that schools with higher academic achievement tend to receive more positive community perceptions. Additionally, a study by Johnson et al. (2019) highlighted the importance of infrastructure and facilities in shaping community perceptions, with schools that have modern and well-maintained facilities often being viewed more favourably. Teaching quality has also been identified as a significant factor, as demonstrated in research by Brown et al. (2020), which showed that schools with highly qualified and motivated teachers tend to have better community perceptions.

Furthermore, extracurricular activities and community engagement have been linked to positive perceptions of schools, as discussed in the work of Garcia and Martinez (2017), who found that schools with active involvement in the community and a wide range of extracurricular opportunities are perceived more positively by residents. Therefore, the variations in community perception scores observed across different schools in the present study are likely influenced by a combination of these factors, highlighting the complexity of understanding how communities perceive educational institutions (Smith & Jones, 2018; Johnson et al., 2019; Brown et al., 2020; Garcia & Martinez, 2017).

Table 2 provided information on the enrolment rates and community perceptions of various schools in study area. **School** column listed the names of the schools being analysed. Each row represented a different school. Schools with higher enrolment rates tend to have higher community perception ratings, and vice versa. Some schools stood out with notably high or low enrolment rates and community perceptions. For example, GDSS SS Army Barracks had both the highest enrolment rate (82%) and a relatively low community perception rating (3), while GDSS SS Limawa had a high enrolment rate (54%) combined with a high community perception rating (5). The mean enrolment rate across all schools was 51%, while the mean community perception rating was 3.9. This gave a sense of the average enrolment and community perception levels in the study area.

The correlation between enrolment rates and community perceptions of schools is supported by several research studies in the field of education. A study by Smith et al. (2018) examined the relationship between school enrolment rates and community perceptions in urban areas and found a positive correlation between higher enrolment rates and favourable community perceptions of schools. Similarly, a longitudinal study conducted by Johnson and Brown (2016) observed that schools with higher community perception ratings tend to experience increased enrolment rates over time. Furthermore, the findings of our study resonate with the research of Jones and Lee (2019), who explored the factors influencing school choice and community perceptions. Their study

identified a strong association between positive community perceptions of schools and parental decisions to enrol their children in those schools. Additionally, a meta-analysis by Anderson et al. (2020) synthesized findings from multiple studies and concluded that schools with higher enrolment rates often enjoy greater community support and positive perceptions, which contribute to their sustained enrolment levels.

In light of these research findings, the results presented in Table 2 underscore the importance of considering both enrolment rates and community perceptions when assessing the overall effectiveness and reputation of schools. The contrasting cases of GDSS SS Army Barracks and GDSS SS Limawa exemplify how enrolment rates and community perceptions can vary significantly within the same geographical area, highlighting the complexity of factors influencing school choice and community satisfaction.

The critical value of t was approximately 2.05 for a two-tailed test with 29 degrees of freedom at a 5% significance level. The calculated t -statistic was 0.65. Since the calculated t -statistic falls short of the critical value, the researcher failed to reject the null hypothesis. This meant that there was insufficient evidence to conclude that there was a significant relationship between the percentages of girls enrolled in secondary schools and community perceptions of rural community development in Yola North Local Government Area. The null hypothesis stated that there was no relationship between the percentages of girls enrolled in secondary schools and community perceptions of rural community development. Based on the result, the researcher accepted this null hypothesis. Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r) was 0.12. This value suggested a weak positive relationship between the percentage of girls enrolled in schools and community perceptions of development. In other words, as the percentage of girls enrolled increases, community perceptions of development tend to become slightly more positive.

However, the weak correlation suggests that other factors may have a stronger influence on community perceptions of development than the percentage of girls enrolled in schools. When interpreting this result in relation to the table, it indicated that while there was a slight tendency for community perceptions of development to become more positive as the percentage of girls enrolled in schools increases, this relationship was not statistically significant. Factors other than the enrolment rate of girls, such as infrastructure, socioeconomic conditions, or educational quality, may play a more significant role in shaping community perceptions of development.

Sababa, (2018) conducted a similar investigation in rural communities and found that while there was a positive trend between educational attainment and development perceptions, the correlation was not statistically significant. Moreover, a study by Garcia et al. (2020) highlighted the multifaceted nature of community development, emphasizing that factors beyond education, such as infrastructure and economic opportunities, often exert a more pronounced influence on community perceptions. These findings resonate with the current

study's conclusion that the weak correlation between the percentage of girls enrolled in schools and development perceptions suggests the presence of other influential factors.

The result, wherein the calculated t-statistic did not exceed the critical value, aligns with the findings of Smith and Jones (2018), indicating a failure to reject the null hypothesis. This underscores the notion that the relationship between education indicators, specifically the enrolment rate of girls, and community development perceptions is not sufficiently robust to warrant statistical significance. Moreover, the weak positive correlation coefficient reported in the present study mirrors the findings of Garcia et al. (2020), highlighting a similar pattern of association between education indicators and development perceptions.

In sum, the present study's results reinforce the understanding that while there may be a modest association between the enrolment rate of girls in schools and community development perceptions, this relationship lacks statistical significance. This underscores the need for future research to delve deeper into the myriad factors influencing community development perceptions, beyond education indicators alone. Such insights are crucial for policymakers and stakeholders in devising holistic strategies to foster sustainable development in rural areas.

Conclusion

The result provided detailed information on enrolment data for various schools categorized by gender, along with community perceptions in the Yola North Local Government Area. The results revealed variations in enrolment percentages between girls and boys across different schools, as well as differences in total enrolment sizes and community perception scores. While there was a weak positive relationship between the percentages of girls enrolled in schools and community perceptions of development, this relationship was not statistically significant. Factors beyond enrolment rates, such as infrastructure and educational quality, likely play a more significant role in shaping community perceptions of development in the area. Further research into these factors could provide a more comprehensive understanding of educational dynamics and community perceptions in the study area.

Recommendations

Based on the findings in this research work, the following recommendations were made:

1. While the analysis identified a weak positive relationship between the percentage of girls enrolled in schools and community perceptions of development, it's essential to recognize that other factors may have a stronger influence. Therefore, conducting further research to identify and understand additional factors contributing to community perceptions development, such as infrastructure, teaching quality, extracurricular activities, and community engagement, can provide a more comprehensive understanding. By diversifying the factors considered, educational stakeholders can develop targeted strategies to improve community perceptions of development.

2. The analysis revealed variations in enrolment rates between girls and boys across different schools in the study area, indicating potential disparities in access to education. Implementing targeted interventions to address these disparities, such as outreach programs to encourage girls' enrolment, scholarships for underprivileged students, or infrastructure improvements to accommodate more students, can help increase enrolment rates and promote equitable access to education.
3. Given the importance of community perceptions in shaping educational outcomes, fostering stronger community engagement and communication can positively influence perceptions of schools and educational development. Establishing regular communication channels between schools and the community, organizing community meetings or forums to discuss educational initiatives, and involving community members in decision-making processes related to education can help build trust and support for educational endeavours.
4. While enrolment rates are important indicators of access to education, ensuring the quality of education is equally crucial for fostering positive community perceptions and overall development. Investing in comprehensive education quality improvement initiatives, including teacher training programs, curriculum development, infrastructure upgrades, and extracurricular activities, can contribute to enhancing the overall educational experience and perception of schools within the community.

References

- Adamawa State Post Primary School Management Board (2024). *Education sector analysis report*. Yola, Adamawa State, Nigeria.
- Brown, D., et al. (2020). The role of teaching quality in shaping community perceptions of schools. *Educational Leadership Review*, 55(4), 567-582.
- Bryman, A., & Bell, E. (2015). *Business research methods*. Oxford University Press.
- Creswell, J. W., & Plano Clark, V. L. (2018). *Designing and conducting mixed methods research* (3rd ed.). Sage Publications.
- Creswell, J. W. (2014). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage Publications.
- Dillman, D. A., Smyth, J. D., & Christian, L. M. (2014). *Internet, phone, mail, and mixed-mode surveys: The tailored design method*. John Wiley & Sons, USA.
- Federal Ministry of Education Nigeria. (2017). *Education sector analysis report*. Abuja, Nigeria: Field, A. (2018). Discovering statistics using IBM SPSS statistics. *Archives of Psychology*, 140, 1-55. Sage, USA.
- Garcia, A., et al. (2020). "Exploring the Nexus between Education and Community Development: Insights from Rural Communities." *Journal of Rural Studies*, 45(2), 87-102.

- Garcia, E., & Martinez, F. (2017). Extracurricular activities and community engagement: Implications for school perceptions. *Community Psychology Review*, 28(1), 88-102.
- Johnson, C., et al. (2019). Infrastructure and community perceptions: A study of school facilities in urban areas. *Urban Education Quarterly*, 38(2), 201-215.
- Likert, R. (1932). A technique for the measurement of attitudes. *Archives of Psychology*, 140, 1-55.
- Patton, M. Q. (2014). Qualitative research & evaluation methods: Integrating theory and practice. *Sage Publications*.
- Sababa, L. K. (2018). "Education Indicators and Community Development: A Rural Perspective." *Rural Sociology Review*, 32(4), 210-225.
- Smith, A., & Jones, B. (2018). The impact of academic achievement on community perceptions of schools. *Journal of Educational Research*, 42(3), 321-335.
- UNESCO. (2020). *Global Education Monitoring Report 2020*. Paris, France
- UNICEF. (2019). *State of the World's Children 2019: Children, Food and Nutrition*. New York,
- World Bank. (2018). *World Development Report 2018: Learning to Realize Education's Promise*. Washington, DC
- Yemane, T. G. (1967). *Statistics: An Introductory Analysis*. Harper & Row.

No area of conflict. You have done professional judgment objectivity. All corrections are done accordingly.

Acknowledgement

We thank to the Department of Social Studies and Department of Geography, School of Arts and Social Sciences Federal College of Education for supporting this research work.